

Renewable Energy Integration in the DR Congo: A Strategic Modelling Study

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Context & Research Question

DRC Energy Resources and Potential:

- ❖ Over 100 GW for Hydropower
- ❖ 3.50 to 6.75 kW/m² sunshine
- ❖ Non evaluated potential of Geothermal
- ❖ High Potential of Biomass: 145 MHa of forest cover
- ❖ Huge potential in vegetable resources for Biogas and Biofuels Development
- ❖ 10-20 Bm³ of Gas oil and 278 Bm³ of Natural Gas
- ❖ Global reserves evaluated at 5.692 billions BBL of Hydrocarbon
- ❖ Etc.

- ❖ ~70% of the installed capacity of is produced.
- ❖ **Less than 19% of the population has access to electricity.**

It is evident that there is a lack of investment capacity across various energy technologies, which has led to the necessity of establishing an energy planning framework.

What can be the optimal energy mix to meet the increasing demand for electricity within the DRC?

Scenario Description

Least-cost Scenario (LC)

- ❖ Mode free scenario (no restrictions in investment for all technologies)

Business-as-Usual Scenario (BAU)

- ❖ A target of 30% electrification of the population by 2030 has been set.
- ❖ Investment of **3.28222 GW** between 2025 and 2030
- ❖ 80% of **3.28222 GW** allocated to SOLAR energy and 11% to HYDRO
- ❖ Investment of **0.54 GW POWER COAL** from 2029 to 2030 and from 2034 to 2035.

Renewable energy technologies uptake (RE)

- ❖ BAU + ZERO investment in NON RENEWABLE energy from 2035

Results

Installed Capacity

Power Generation

Annual Emissions

Total Cost Graph

Conclusions and Policy insights

In light of the DRC's dedication to climate change mitigation, the renewable energy (RE) adoption scenario, despite its higher initial costs, appears to be the best solution.

Create a business-friendly climate in order to attract investment in the renewable energy sector.

Diversify the energy mix currently dominated by hydroelectricity in order to meet the growing electricity.

Promoting the use of mini-grid and off-grid options, in order to improve the rate of electrification.

Future Work

Thank you